

HUMILIATION, ABUSE, AND DEATH LIVE ON AIR

WHO HAS FAILED
THE STREAMER
JEAN PORMANOVE?

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Abstract

This article examines the death of French streamer “Jean Pormanove”, who died live on the platform Kick after 12 days of on-camera abuse, watched by thousands and monetised in real time. It reconstructs the chain of accountability that made this tragedy possible and analyses the failures of multiple actors with the power to intervene: the platform, the media regulator, judicial and police authorities, and political leaders. Their combined inaction enabled the sustained exploitation, until death, of a vulnerable individual on a major live streaming platform. Through a socio-legal analysis, the article shows how this case exposes the limits of the EU’s digital governance model, whose effectiveness depends less on legislative sophistication than on the willingness and capacity of institutions to enforce it. Using “shock” as a central analytical lens, the paper explores its dual role as a driver of online visibility and an emerging regulatory concern. It concludes that without meaningful enforcement, the promise of a safer digital environment will remain largely illusory.

Content Note

This article contains descriptions of violence, and psychological and physical abuse, including accounts of real events involving the death of a man.

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1. Introduction

During the night of 17 August 2025, French streamer Raphaël Graven, known under the pseudonym of Jean Pormanove or “JP”, died during a live stream, following 12 days of continuous on-camera humiliation and abuse. The broadcast had thousands of concurrent viewers, trended on social media, and generated significant revenue through audience donations. Yet, no meaningful intervention occurred. Not by the platform hosting the content, Kick, nor by the media regulator, the justice, police, or political authorities. His death, though officially not ruled a homicide, was the predictable culmination of a sustained campaign of exploitation, lasting for months, and made possible by a permissive platform and inadequate enforcement of the European Union’s flagship digital regulation: the Digital Services Act (DSA).

That such a tragedy could occur in one of the most regulated digital market in the world is troubling. Over the past decade, EU institutions have invested unprecedented political capital into building a comprehensive framework for online accountability: the DSA, the Digital Markets Act, and a suite of complementary measures designed to curb platform excesses and protect users from harm. Despite this ambition, a man could be abused live on one of the world’s largest live streaming platforms without effective intervention. How, amid so much regulation, is it still possible for someone to slip through the cracks? This is the central question that animates this paper.

Through a socio-legal analysis, the notion of “shock” serves as the paper’s central analytical thread. It is used here in a dual sense. First, as a strategy deliberately employed by creators and platforms to attract visibility, engagement, and profit. Second, as a reporting category used to identify and report harmful or degrading material, such as that recognised by one of France’s Trusted Flaggers under the DSA. As such, shock occupies an ambivalent position: it is simultaneously a normalised practice in online spaces and an emerging regulatory concern.

The case of Jean Pormanove provides a powerful lens through which to explore this tension. His death was not an isolated aberration hidden in the dark corners of the Internet, but rather a symptom of a system that enables to convert shock into economic value. The fact that the live stream continued uninterrupted until death raises urgent questions about the limits of digital governance, the true enforcement capacity of regulators, and the structural incentives of digital platforms, and their users, that profit from extreme spectacle.

The paper proceeds in two parts. First, it outlines the economic and governance structures underpinning Kick’s business model, including its links to Stake.com and its monetisation of controversial content. It reconstructs the timeline of Jean Pormanove’s abuse and death,

drawing on live stream archives, social media evidence, and journalistic reporting. Second, it analyses the multiple failures across different actors: the platform itself, the French media regulator (ARCOM), the judicial, police and political authorities. Particular attention is paid to how Kick failed to meet the key DSA obligations, including duties of moderation, cooperation with regulators, and accessible and user-friendly reporting mechanisms. While the central argument of this paper concerns Kick's liability under the DSA, the platform's failure to act cannot be examined in isolation from the broader ecosystem of accountability, whose lack of firm action effectively enabled such violations to persist.

At stake here is not only the life of one creator, but the credibility of the EU's digital regulation agenda. The DSA has been heralded as a global gold standard, a bold attempt to shift responsibility onto platforms and build systemic safeguards for Internet users. But as this paper will show, even the most sophisticated regulation fails when platforms are economically disincentivised to act, when responsibility is distributed so widely that it ends up disappearing, and when our politicians look away.

2. Kick's Political Economy of Leniency

a. The Genesis of the Platform

Launched in January 2023 by Australian (now billionaire) entrepreneurs Ed Craven and Bijan Tehrani, Kick positioned itself as a counter-platform to Amazon-owned Twitch, the dominant player in the live streaming market (Santora, 2025). For those less familiar with live streaming, it refers to the real-time broadcast of audiovisual content over the Internet. Its main appeal lies in immediacy and interactivity: audiences can watch events unfold live while engaging directly with the creator (known as the streamer), through a live chat. Viewers can also interact with one another, collectively shaping the direction of the stream and influencing the streamer's next move, blurring the boundary between spectator and participant.

From the outset, Kick pursued an aggressive growth strategy built on financial incentives and strategic controversy. The platform offered creators unusually generous terms: a 95/5 subscription revenue split (compared to the historical 50/50 or 70/30 on Twitch and YouTube) and guaranteed hourly pay for eligible streamers (Rogers, 2023). Kick also entered multi-million-dollar deals with select high-profile creators, the most publicised example being the reported \$100 million non-exclusive, two-year contract with superstar streamer Félix "xQc" Lengyel (Browning, 2023). In addition to these financial incentives, and while its competitor Twitch had progressively formalised its governance model, tightening policies against gambling, hate speech, and sexually explicit content, Kick took the opposite approach. It capitalised on user

frustration with what many Twitch users perceived as overregulation and inconsistent enforcement, and positioned itself as a haven for “free expression”.

Kick actively recruited high-profile, often controversial creators, several of whom had been banned from mainstream platforms: Adin Ross, permanently banned from Twitch for hateful conduct and later revealed as a co-owner of Kick; Ice Poseidon, accused of defrauding followers through a \$500,000 cryptocurrency scheme; gambling-focused streamers such as Corinaakopf and Roshtein (Tsiaoussidis, 2023); and Amouranth, banned multiple times from Twitch and YouTube for sexually explicit content (Cooper, 2025). As a result, Kick quickly became the platform for the Internet outcasts, a space for creators excluded from the mainstream to continue live streaming. Its public message was clear and resonated with familiar libertarian tropes of the platform economy: “creator freedom”, “minimal moderation”, and “no censorship”. Yet, beneath this rhetoric of creative freedom lay a calculated economic design.

Kick is structurally integrated into Stake.com’s global gambling network. Stake.com, founded in 2017 by Kick’s Ed Craven and Bijan Tehrani, is a crypto-backed online casino and sports betting platform licensed in Curaçao, a jurisdiction renowned for its lax gambling regulations and low corporate tax rates (Kunti et al., 2024). Widely regarded as the world’s largest crypto-backed casino, Stake.com operates primarily through cryptocurrency transactions, allowing it to circumvent traditional banking systems and regulatory oversight in many jurisdictions (Schmitt, 2025). The platform’s annual gross gaming revenue¹ went from roughly \$100 million in 2020 to over \$4.7 billion in 2024, a growth fuelled by an aggressive marketing strategy centred on influencer partnerships, most famously with rapper Drake, and high-profile sports sponsorships, including the UFC, Everton Football Club, and the Stake F1 Team Kick Sauber (iGamingToday, 2025). It is now among the largest gambling operators globally, despite crypto-gambling remaining illegal in major markets such as the United States, the United Kingdom and much of Europe (Forbes, 2025).

Kick emerged in direct response to Twitch’s 2022 ban on unlicensed gambling streams and now operates as a traffic funnel directing audiences toward betting activity on Stake.com (Browning, 2023). In October 2025, the platform’s “Slots and Casino” category overwhelmingly dominated viewership, drawing an average of 76,922 concurrent viewers and peaking at over 400,000, figures vastly surpassing Twitch’s equivalent “Slots” category, which averaged just 10,013 viewers with a peak over 35,000. During the same period, Kick’s total average concurrent

¹ Gross gaming revenue is a key metric used by gambling and betting companies which represents the difference between the amount wagered minus the amount won (Corporate Finance Institute, 2025).

audience was around 850,000, compared to Twitch's 1.86 million, meaning that gambling-related content accounted for a disproportionately large share of Kick's total traffic, roughly 16 times higher than on Twitch (Stream Charts, 2025a; TwitchTracker, 2025). Kick's popular creators routinely gamble with accounts funded by online casinos, facing no personal financial risk while profiting through affiliate schemes that reward them for converting viewers into gamblers (Burgess, 2023). This creates a predatory feedback loop: audiences are seduced by the illusion of easy winnings in what are often sponsored or manipulated gambling sessions.

Because of its permissive moderation, lax enforcement and contracts with controversial streamers, Kick has become a refuge for some of the most toxic online content creators. This dynamic is particularly visible in the platform's IRL ("In Real Life") category, which allows streamers to broadcast their everyday activities using portable setups, often just a smartphone, inviting viewers to follow them through what resembles a hybrid experience of real life and online adventure. While IRL streaming has gained popularity across other platforms such as Twitch, Kick's low-regulated environment has amplified its most extreme forms. What unites much of this content is a deliberate pursuit of shock as a strategy to attract attention and generate money.

Some IRL streamers film themselves engaging in disruptive, provocative, or outright dangerous behaviour in public spaces under the guise of "pranks". Over the past year, various of these controversial creators known for their live streams on Kick have made international headlines, particularly across Southeast Asia, which has become a favoured destination for such practices. Streamers exploit the perception that these countries, especially those economically more dependent on tourism, are more lenient toward foreign visitors. In Japan, for example, some streamers have broadcast themselves licking food in restaurants, shouting inflammatory comments about Hiroshima and Nagasaki on public transport, or harassing passersby (Holloway, 2025). "Highlights" of these live streams are then clipped and shared on TikTok, Snapchat, and other short-form video platforms, generating attention around the streamers. This attention can then be converted into money through audience donation or subscriptions.

Following public indignation and sometimes even violent altercations with local populations, some local authorities have begun taking action. By 2025, two high-profile criminal cases have emerged against streamers known for their live streams on Kick. The first involves Johnny Somaly, who is currently facing eight criminal charges in South Korea, ranging from public disturbance to deepfake production, most of which he has reportedly pleaded guilty to (Times of India, 2025). The second concerns Russian content creator Vitaly Zdorovetskiy (Vitalyzdvtv), arrested in the Philippines during a live stream on Kick after allegedly committing a series of

vandalism, theft, and harassment offences. He remains in custody in the Philippines pending trial (Pathak, 2025).²

Of course, spectacle and shock are not new to entertainment. Early reality TV and stunt-based franchises such as *Jackass* (US), *Dirty Sanchez* (UK), or *Les 11 Commandements* with Michaël Youn (France) staged public humiliation, gross-out challenges, and performative risk long before social media existed. Yet, traditional broadcast media operated under editorial control, legal accountability, and tight regulatory oversight. By contrast, what sets Kick apart is the platformisation of these practices in a live, unscripted environment, with little to no real-time supervision and easily circumvented age-gating and content warnings. The core monetisation model of live streaming intensifies these dynamics: the direct financial transactions between viewers and streamers create an immediate incentive for streamers to push boundaries, escalating their behaviour to satisfy, and monetise, the audience's appetite for the extreme. As here in the UK, leading TV broadcasters now struggle to attract around one million viewers during their prime 9pm slots (Savage, 2025), Vitaly Zdorovetskiy could peak at over 80,000 concurrent viewers on his personal channel (Stream Charts, 2025b) and attract several hundreds of thousands unique viewers over the course of one broadcast. More troubling still is the demographic composition of these online audiences, predominantly young men (Similarweb, 2025; WifiTalents, 2025), often highly impressionable and susceptible to emulating bad behaviours. Before his Kick channel was banned, Zdorovetskiy had accumulated over 350,000 followers.

These cases are particularly revealing, as they exemplify the global spread of "patostreaming" or "trash streaming", defined as the live broadcasting of socially deviant or harmful behaviour for entertainment. This phenomenon was first formally identified and studied in Central and Eastern Europe, particularly in Poland (Angielczyk, 2019; Bek & Popiołek, 2019), where it has become a major concern among parents, educators, and policymakers (Polish Safer Internet Centre, 2020). In my PhD research (submitted in 2024),³ I cautioned that Kick's permissive governance model risked globalising this pattern, effectively normalising harmful content under the banner of creative autonomy. The platform's rapid growth and mainstream visibility have since confirmed those concerns, illustrating how commercial incentives and deregulation can together accelerate a race to the bottom in digital culture. With over 850,000 average concurrent viewers,⁴ Kick can no longer be dismissed as a fringe corner of the Internet. It represents a

² It should be noted that both streamers are now banned from Kick.

³ Forthcoming as short-form monograph titled "Musicians on Twitch: Creativity, Struggles, and the Reality Behind Live Streaming" (Anthem Press, 2026).

⁴ For the last 7 days as of 21 October 2025.

symptom of a broader transformation within the attention economy that is increasingly driven by extremity. Within this new system, risk, humiliation and violence have become marketable commodities; spectacle supplants substance, and attention becomes the only worthy currency. This creates an escalatory logic of degeneracy: what shocked audiences yesterday barely registers today. As a result, to remain visible and competitive, creators must constantly push boundaries, become more shocking and often more self-destructive.

a. Jean Pormanove: Life and Death⁵

Jean Pormanove was a French streamer who, like many others during the COVID-19 pandemic, rose to prominence by playing video games and broadcasting his gaming sessions on Twitch. For a long time, he was among the most popular French streamers and held the title of the most-followed French creator on Kick, with 193,000 followers (Stream Charts, 2025c), as well as more than 1.5 million followers combined on his other social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram.

For months preceding his death, Jean Pormanove, 46 years old, had been subjected to mockery, humiliation, and abuse live on camera by two other men, Owen Cenazandotti (known as NarutoVie) and Safine Hamadi (known as Safine), 26 and 23 years old respectively, who routinely struck him, strangled him, doused him with liquids, or deprived him of sleep while live streaming on Kick. Another man, going by the pseudonym of Coudoux, disabled and under legal guardianship, was also used as a target of violence and ridicule by NarutoVie and Safine as well as occasional guests who joined their sessions. The group's dynamic was ritualised: the two leaders, NarutoVie and Safine, acted as instigators and bullies; Jean Pormanove was the main target, the "punching bag", whose occasional acts of defiance fuelled both the aggression of his abusers and the excitement of viewers; Coudoux, more docile, served as a secondary scapegoat. While both JP and Coudoux appeared to participate willingly in the action, their vulnerable situations suggest that they might have been exploited.

The collective of streamers operated under the name "Lokal" and spent their days together in the same house located in the South of France, a setup reminiscent of the early YouTube "creator houses" such as FaZe Clan, where content creators cohabite to maximise content production. In Lokal's case, however, this cohabitation produced not just collaboration but also sadistic coercion. The live streams mostly took place in what appeared to be a windowless basement, lit

⁵ To reconstruct the events leading to the death of Jean Pormanove, I relied on multiple sources, including archived live streams circulated on platforms such as TikTok and YouTube, online forums and Discord communities. This material was complemented by journalistic reporting, which is cited as appropriate. As most of these sources were in French, my native fluency provided a significant advantage.

by harsh artificial lights that gave the scene a claustrophobic, horror-movie tone. The walls were dirty; the atmosphere resembled a makeshift squat more than a content production studio. Streamers sat in front of the camera, performing all sorts of “challenges”, some of which humiliating and violent, where the audience could decide, in exchange of money, what bodily harm to inflict to Jean Pormanove and Coudoux. The live chat, populated by mostly young men coming from all socio-economic backgrounds, from financiers and bankers to manual labourers, typically overflowed with slurs and incitements to violence. Since 2024, this had been the recurring theme of the group’s broadcasts.

In August 2025, the “Lokal” organised one of their marathon streams, a format that has become increasingly popular among streamers, involving continuous live streaming over several days and nights while setting challenges to entertain viewers and maximise donations. In this instance, the group organised a 10-day continuous live stream during which they were physically chained together, pledging collectively at the outset not to abandon the challenge and aiming to raise as much money as possible. To stimulate donations from the virulent audience, the group subjected Jean Pormanove, and to a lesser extent Coudoux, to a series of humiliating and violent “challenges” for money. These included: slapping and punching them in the face, pulling their hair, shocking them with an electric dog collar, forcing them to clean toilets after another member’s defecation, parading them through the streets with sexual placards, repeated verbal abuse, and exploiting nicotine addiction as a means of humiliation, among many other things (Kezzouf, 2025).

On the seventh day of this marathon, Jean Pormanove sent a desperate message to his mother, claiming that he was being held against his will. The group later mocked this plea live on air, reading it aloud to thousands of viewers while continuing the broadcast. Although JP repeatedly expressed a desire to leave, he appeared psychologically unable to do so, suggesting a form of coercive control. According to former colleagues and friends, he was known to be psychologically fragile and highly susceptible to manipulation (Jaziri-Prédignac and Bonnetier, 2025).

After 298 hours of this continuous and particularly violent marathon stream, with nearly 40,000 euros collected by the group, Jean Pormanove died in his sleep, live on camera, while his companions slept beside him. In a macabre twist, it was the viewers who first noticed something was wrong. Through donations that triggered sound alerts in the bedroom, a form of interactive torture mechanic popularised on TikTok where audiences pay to disturb streamers, viewers tried to wake the group. When his companions finally stirred, they attempted to wake JP up by throwing objects at him, one last humiliation, before shaking him, laughing at first, assuming it

was a prank. Moments later, when they realised he was unresponsive, they ended the stream. It was over.

The autopsy revealed that the death “had no traumatic origin and was not linked to the intervention of a third party”, stated the Public Prosecutor of Nice in an official statement, adding that “the probable causes of death therefore appear to be medical and/or toxicological in nature” (Pelais, 2025). Readers may draw their own conclusions as to whether months of humiliation and abuse may have contributed to this outcome.

3. Where Does Accountability Lie?

a. The Platform

How can such a tragedy occur when the harm has been unfolding, live, for months, in plain sight?

At first glance, one might assume that Jean Pormanove’s death went unnoticed, the tragic outcome of an obscure and marginal corner of the Internet. In reality, it is the opposite. Data shows that from January 2025 to the death on 18 August 2025, Jean Pormanove stood out as Kick’s leading French streamer by nearly every metric. He was the only French creator to exceed 10 million hours watched (far ahead of the runner-up’s 6 million) and his streams averaged over 8,500 live viewers, more than twice the audience of his nearest competitor (Stream Charts, 2025c). During the 12-day marathon broadcast leading up to his death, the channel averaged 9,556 concurrent viewers. In other words, nearly ten thousand people were watching at any given moment, day and night, for nearly two weeks (Stream Charts, 2025d). This level of sustained audience engagement is high, even by professional live streaming standards, and underscores the visibility of the abuse taking place.

The DSA is the most relevant legislative instrument for assessing Kick’s potential liability in the case of Jean Pormanove’s death. Entering into force in November 2022 and becoming directly applicable in February 2024, the DSA updates and builds upon the liability regime established under the 2000 e-Commerce Directive. Whereas the earlier framework focused primarily on shielding intermediaries from liability for third-party content, the DSA reflects a fundamental shift towards accountability for digital services. It moves beyond the narrow question of when platforms are legally liable for illegal content to address how they design their systems, moderate content, and mitigate foreseeable risks to users and society. Against this backdrop, the fact that such extreme content could remain visible and monetised for months, produced by one of the platform’s most prominent channel, suggests a profound failure of both corporate responsibility and regulatory enforcement.

To begin, Kick's own Community Guidelines, as with most similar online platforms (e.g. Twitch, YouTube) recognise its responsibility to intervene when harm, humiliation, and abuse are broadcast:

While violence may be contextual and there can be varying degrees of impact, we do not permit content that depicts or incites abhorrent violence including significant harm, suffering or death. We further do not allow malicious trolling, harassment or brigading. [...] On the other hand, being actively involved in the participation of content which contravenes these Guidelines is more severe. [...] Violations of these Community Guidelines are, by default, a violation of our Terms of Service.

Under the DSA, such self-regulatory commitments are not merely ethical aspirations but binding legal obligations. Article 14 requires online intermediaries to set out their content moderation policies in clear and accessible terms, and to apply them "in a diligent, objective and proportionate manner", with due regard for users' rights and legitimate interests. This provision anchors platforms' responsibilities in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, which enshrines the inviolability of human dignity (Article 1), the right to physical and mental integrity (Article 3), and prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment (Article 4).

Despite these clear rules, and the visibility and duration of the abuse streamed on Jean Pormanove's channel, no moderation action was taken throughout the 12 days the marathon broadcast remained live. Kick only banned the channel after the death, likely as a precautionary measure: once a channel is removed, its replays, clips, and statistics disappear along with it. Kick also deleted past posts on X that made references to Jean Pormanove and the group "Lokal".

Under Article 6 of the DSA, hosting providers such as Kick benefit from a conditional exemption from liability for user-generated content only insofar as they lack actual knowledge of illegal activity or content, or upon obtaining such knowledge act expeditiously to remove or disable access to it. In the case of Jean Pormanove's death, there is substantial evidence suggesting that Kick both was aware of the illegal conduct and had the capacity to intervene, yet failed to do so.

Article 6 of the DSA largely reproduces the conditional safe harbour first established in Article 14 of the 2000 e-Commerce Directive and interpreted by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in *L'Oréal v eBay* (C-324/09). In that judgment, the CJEU held that a hosting provider loses the liability exemption when it plays an active role giving it knowledge or control over user content, such as by optimising presentation or promoting certain material, and that even a formally passive host cannot rely on the exemption if it was aware of facts or circumstances from which a diligent economic operator would have realised the illegality and failed to act expeditiously (Arnold, 2020). Jean Pormanove's channel, and the "Lokal" collective more broadly,

ranked among the most-viewed content on the platform globally and appeared on its recommendation feeds. Kick's algorithmic classification and commercial promotion of these streams constitute precisely the kind of optimisation that removes a platform from the category of a passive intermediary. This principle was, however, narrowed in *YouTube and Cyando (Joined Cases C-682/18 and C-683/18)*, where the CJEU ruled that algorithmic categorisation, personalisation, ranking, or search functionality do not, by themselves, confer specific knowledge of illegality. Also in that judgment, though delivered in the context of copyright, the CJEU confirmed that platforms lose their exemption if they participate in selecting unlawful content or, despite knowing or having reason to know that users are making illegal material available, fail to adopt appropriate and effective technological measures expected from a reasonably diligent operator (Husovec, 2024).

Applied to Jean Pormanove's case, this reasoning is directly relevant. Even if Kick were to be treated as "passive", the persistent visibility of broadcasts depicting humiliation, coercion, and physical abuse would have made their illegality apparent to any diligent economic operator, triggering the duty to act expeditiously under Article 6 of the DSA. Furthermore, Kick had previously banned Jean Pormanove's channel, indicating that it had reviewed and sanctioned the content in the past. The platform's official French account on X shared and repurposed images of JP, including one showing him covered in paint, to promote merchandise, and joked on X about a "challenge" in which JP was coerced into a fake marriage with Coudoux for entertainment (DéphaseuR, 2025). Kick's co-founder Ed Craven was also listed among Jean Pormanove channel's highest donors, having gifted 150 subscriptions at the time of his death (Steedman, 2025). Such conduct demonstrates both awareness and tacit endorsement of the group's activities and points to breaches of multiple DSA obligations. Article 23 requires platforms to suspend, after prior warning, users who repeatedly disseminate manifestly illegal content. The temporary suspension of Jean Pormanove could not be regarded as a proportionate response to such sustained and egregious violations. Additionally, Article 18 imposes a separate duty on hosting providers to notify law enforcement when they become aware of information giving rise to a suspicion that a criminal offence involving a threat to a person's life or safety "has taken place, is taking place, or is likely to take place". Given the frequency and prominence of the abuse happening on the channel, it could easily be argued that this threshold was met.

Moreover, the platform also appears to have failed to comply with its obligations regarding user reporting mechanisms. Article 16 of the DSA requires hosting providers to establish accessible and user-friendly procedures enabling any individual or entity to notify the presence of allegedly illegal content. Such mechanisms must allow notifiers to submit a substantiated explanation and

to confirm, in good faith, the accuracy of their allegations. In practice, however, Kick's reporting interface was (and still is) accessible only to registered users and provided no space for submitting explanations, attaching supporting evidence, or identifying the basis of the complaint. This observation is based on my own testing of the platform's reporting system in October 2025, and on archived videos dating from before the incident that show the same restricted process. Such design clearly falls short of the procedural standards prescribed by Article 16 effectively restricting the right of notification to account-holders and preventing third parties, including victims or observers, from reporting manifestly illegal content.

This deficiency also rendered Article 22 of the DSA effectively inoperative, as it directly compromised the functioning of the Trusted Flaggers mechanism. Under this provision, platforms are required to put in place the technical and organisational systems necessary to ensure that reports submitted by Trusted Flaggers, the entities formally designated by national Digital Services Coordinators (DSC) for their expertise in identifying specific types of illegal content, are treated with priority and resolved without undue delay. As confirmed by the archived versions of Kick's website available through the Wayback Machine, the platform had no operational framework for Trusted Flaggers and no designated reporting channel for the submission of priority notices at the time of the incident. A DSA Information Guide was only added to Kick's Safety Hub on 28 August 2025, followed at an undetermined later date by a Trusted Flagger Onboarding page. The timing is particularly revealing: in its H2 2024 Transparency Report, covering the period from 1 July to 31 December 2024, Kick declared that it had "received zero reports from trusted flaggers during the reporting period" and stated that it was "prepared to enrol trusted flaggers into [its] content moderation program to provide a dedicated reporting channel once they have been designated" (Kick, 2024). This is inconsistent with the regulatory timeline, as in France, the first Trusted Flagger was officially designated on 6 November 2024 (ARCOM, 2024). The discrepancy demonstrates that Kick was not merely awaiting designations, as it claimed, but had failed to implement the required measures to enable Trusted Flaggers to operate, thereby remaining non-compliant with Articles 16 and 22 of the DSA.

Lastly, there are also some concerns about Kick's compliance with the transparency obligations set out in Article 24 of the DSA, which require all online platforms to submit their statements of reasons to the DSA Transparency Database each time content is removed or restricted. Despite reporting in its H2 2024 Transparency Report that it had actioned 11,863 items of content in violation of its Community Guidelines, Kick has not uploaded any corresponding statements of reasons to the database. The discrepancy appears to stem from the platform's own self-

classification: according to its DSA Information Guide, last updated in October 2025, Kick describes itself merely as a “standard intermediary and hosting service”, implicitly denying its status as an “online platform” within the meaning of Article 3 of the DSA (Kick, 2025). Yet, this self-assessment is contradicted by the company’s H2 2024 Transparency Report, which, in regard to training measures for its moderation staff, explicitly acknowledges “the specialised nature of live streaming and the difficulties inherent in moderating an online platform”. The contradiction between these two descriptions reveals the broader lack of internal coherence that characterise the platform’s compliance approach.

This set of failures to comply with the DSA obligations exposes a broader structural problem: the tension between regulatory expectations of responsibility and the economic logic of the attention economy. Jean Pormanove’s channel was among the most-watched on the platform, generating enormous traffic and visibility. For a platform like Kick, visibility translates directly into value: every viewer contributes to its market share, boosts its appeal to advertisers,⁶ and enhances its bargaining power with investors. Intervention, particularly against a high-performing channel, thus runs counter to the platform’s core economic incentives.

The DSA and similar frameworks are built on the assumption that platforms will comply with moderation obligations because the legal and reputational costs of non-compliance outweigh the benefits of inaction. When platforms derive direct or indirect value from transgressive and harmful content, the calculus can reverse, and the DSA’s logic collapses. The issue, therefore, extends beyond mere non-compliance, and lies in the paradox that some platforms grow precisely by refusing responsibility for the environments they create and exploit. The DSA, through Article 52, does provide for fines of up to 6% of global annual turnover. For platforms like Kick, backed by billionaire founders and connected to high-revenue sectors such as online gambling, symbolic fines or reputational damage might be unlikely to shift behaviour. Only when the cost of negligence exceeds the profit of visibility will platforms be meaningfully incentivised to act. Otherwise, compliance will remain selective and responsibility performative.

b. Media Regulator

It would be too easy to place all the blame on the platform. As the previous section has shown, Kick’s negligence is undeniable, yet the harm it enabled did not occur in a vacuum, raising serious questions about regulatory oversight.

⁶ Though, unlike most mainstream social media and live streaming platforms, Kick does not feature structural advertising as of now (i.e., pre-roll, mid-roll, or algorithmically targeted ads integrated into the platform interface).

Under Article 51 of the DSA, Digital Services Coordinators within each Member State are entrusted with monitoring and enforcing compliance by online platforms operating within their jurisdiction, therefore centralising accountability in a single national authority while enhancing collaborations between Member States. This represents a significant innovation of the DSA which establishes DSCs as empowered regulators with defined and heightened investigative and enforcement powers, the ability to request information, conduct inspections, impose sanctions, and cooperate with other Member States and the European Commission to ensure that the DSA is respected. In France, this responsibility falls to the ARCOM. Given Kick's sustained presence in the French market and the visibility of Jean Pormanove streams, the ARCOM's apparent inaction is striking.

Following a December 2024 investigation by Mediapart,⁷ journalists tried to contact the ARCOM to expose the case but were left with no answer. Six months before Jean Pormanove's death, the French NGO Human Rights League (Ligue des droits de l'Homme) had also sounded the alarm, formally referring Kick to the ARCOM, warning of the platform's lax moderation practices. The referral explicitly named Jean Pormanove's channel, stating that the channel:

features vulnerable individuals in videos of a humiliating nature, mixing mockery, violence and physical abuse, with the aim of broadcasting their reactions, acclaimed by an especially aggressive audience. These acts are in fact real acts of violence that could correspond to criminal offences. (LDH, 2025)

The language leaves little room for interpretation: this was not parody or performance, but real violence.

The core reason for the ARCOM's inability to intervene may lie in a jurisdictional void created by Kick's failure to comply with Article 13 of the DSA. This provision requires any platform offering services within the EU to designate a legal representative and a point of contact established in the EU to facilitate communication between the platforms and the DSCs. However, at the time of the incident, in August 2025, Kick, an Australian-based platform, had no such representative, despite the German DSC, Bundesnetzagentur, formally asking Kick to appoint a legal representative in the EU in 2024 (Datta and Lomas, 2025). Without a legal representative in the EU, the ARCOM argued that it was unable to serve or enforce an order for content removal under Article 9 of the DSA (Hembert, 2025). Article 9 establishes a formal mechanism through which national judicial or administrative authorities (ARCOM being a national independent administrative public authority) can issue orders requiring platforms to remove or disable access to specific illegal content. Such orders must clearly identify the content in question, explain the

⁷ One of the largest and most reputable French investigative media.

legal basis for its illegality, and specify the territorial scope and deadlines for compliance. Crucially, these orders must be addressed to the platform's designated legal representative within the EU, meaning that, in the absence of one, enforcement mechanisms effectively fail, as national regulators have no entity to formally notify or hold accountable. Only on 29 August 2025, 11 days after the death, the Malta Communications Authority received a formal notification from Kick to designate a legal representative in Malta (MCA, 2025).

Despite Kick's failure to comply with Article 13 of the DSA, the incident may be viewed as a failure on the part of the French DSC, whose enforcement powers under the DSA are significantly strengthened. Pursuant to Article 51 of the DSA, where a DSC determines that a provider of intermediary services has not sufficiently complied with its obligations, that the infringement remains unremedied and continues to cause serious harm, and that such infringement involves a criminal offence threatening life or safety, the DSC may request that the competent judicial authority order the temporary restriction of access for recipients to the infringing service, or, where technically infeasible, to the online interface of the provider. In other words, the DSA explicitly empowers DSCs not only to monitor compliance but to initiate coercive measures in cases of persistent and harmful non-compliance. Kick's H1 2024 Transparency Report (Kick, 2024) indicates that the platform received four formal information requests from EU Member States, including two from French authorities, suggesting that official communication channels with the company did in fact exist prior to the incident. This evidence undermines the notion that Kick was entirely beyond regulatory reach and implies that ARCOM or other French authorities possessed at least a minimal capacity to engage with the platform.

Furthermore, although Kick itself was not established within the EU and had no legal representative at the time of the events, it leases its technological infrastructure from Amazon Web Services (AWS) (Craig, 2023), whose data-hosting and content-delivery services underpin the Kick's operation. AWS as a hosting service provider must also maintain a legal representative and point of contact within the EU for the purpose of regulatory cooperation under Article 13 of the DSA. This re-opens, at least in principle, a jurisdictional channel through which the ARCOM could have sought cooperation or notification under Article 9 of the DSA. Although the DSA distinguishes between hosting service providers (such as AWS) and online platforms (such as Kick), both fall within the broader category of intermediary services subject to EU obligations. In consequence, while Kick would be the direct recipient of an order to act against illegal content, AWS could be viewed as the indirect intermediary responsible for storing and transmitting that content and, therefore, bound by the due-diligence duties applicable to hosting providers under Articles 6, 9, and 16 of the DSA. It could be argued that AWS, through its established legal

representative and contact point in the EU under Article 13 of the DSA, could have served as an indirect channel for compliance, enabling EU authorities to transmit a takedown demand through a legally reachable intermediary. More informally, given that AWS and Kick maintain an ongoing commercial relationship, and that AWS has offices and staff in France, it is not unreasonable to argue that AWS could have created a link between the ARCOM and Kick through business networks.

In light of this, the ARCOM's inaction raises serious questions regarding the scope and exercise of its regulatory mandate. As France's designated DSC, the ARCOM had both the competence and the legal basis to act more assertively once it became evident that Kick lacked legal representation within the EU in breach of Article 13 of the DSA. Given the nature of the infringement and given that Kick actively targets French users through dedicated communication channels, the platform's presence in the national digital environment was neither incidental nor peripheral. It could therefore be argued that the ARCOM should have exercised its investigative and enforcement prerogatives under Articles 51 of the DSA, including requesting judicial intervention or coordinating with the European Board for Digital Services to compel compliance. Its inaction thus reflects not merely a procedural gap but a broader failure of enforcement, whereby the DSA's enhanced supervisory powers remained dormant when the risk to individual safety and public trust was most acute.

c. Judicial & Police Authorities

The failure to protect Jean Pormanove also reflects the inaction of the institutions tasked with upholding justice and safeguarding citizens.

Several provisions of the French Penal Code appear directly relevant and should have triggered a swift response. The videos depicting repeated humiliation and physical violence could fall under Article 222-1, which criminalises acts of torture and barbarity; Article 222-33-3 extends criminal liability to anyone who knowingly records or disseminates images showing such acts; and Article 223-15-2 punishes the fraudulent exploitation of a person's weakness or vulnerability, with aggravated penalties when committed via an online service or by an organised group.

By early 2025, eight months before the streamer's death, reports concerning his channel had already reached the highest levels of French law enforcement. According to Clara Chappaz, then Minister for AI and Digital Technologies, the PHAROS platform, France's official portal for reporting illegal online content, had received over 80 separate alerts about the channel (Turcan and Kezzouf, 2025). Following the investigation by Mediapart in December 2024, the public prosecutor of Nice opened an inquiry. In January 2025, both NarutoVie and Safine, the two

bullies, were questioned by the police but released without charge. JP and Coudoux were also questioned and reportedly told investigators that “the events were part of a performance intended to create buzz and make money”. According to the public prosecutor, all four denied any wrongdoing and refused medical or psychiatric examinations, insisting they were “completely free in their movements and decisions” (Gabriel et al., 2025). In resurfaced clips, Jean Pormanove admitted that he remained with the group primarily for financial reasons. In the month preceding his death, police reportedly visited the filming location on five separate occasions (Turcan and Kezzouf, 2025).

Why these repeated visits failed to produce formal action remains unclear. On the one hand, the PHAROS unit which processed over 222,000 reports in 2024 (Ministère de l'Intérieur, 2025) has long suffered from chronic underfunding and resource constraints, despite its crucial role in the fight against online harm. Police unions have repeatedly denounced the inadequacy of its equipment: the 49 officers operate on low-bandwidth connections and often rely on free, unofficial software to download evidence from social networks because licence renewals are left unpaid (Molinie, 2024). It is plausible that investigators struggled to capture the necessary proof, particularly given the ephemeral nature of live streamed content, which complicates evidence preservation (even though numerous clips and archived videos were publicly accessible online).

Nonetheless, the DSA would have been directly relevant in assisting the judicial authorities to suspend the channel. Under Article 9(1), once a relevant national judicial or administrative authority issues an order identifying specific items of illegal content under national or Union law, the provider of intermediary services must act without undue delay and notify the authority of the measures taken, specifying when and how the order was executed. Article 9(2) sets out detailed conditions for such orders: they must specify the legal basis and reasons for the illegality, identify the authority issuing the order, provide precise information enabling the intermediary to locate the content (e.g. URL), and indicate redress mechanisms available to both the provider and the user uploading the content. They must also delimit their territorial scope to what is strictly necessary to achieve their objective, ensuring proportionality, and must be transmitted in the declared language and through the electronic point of contact designated by the provider pursuant to Article 11 of the DSA. In the case of Jean Pormanove, an order under Article 9 could have been issued by the public prosecutor ordering Kick to suspend the channel, citing Articles 222-1, 222-33-3 and 223-15-2 of the French Penal Code as the substantive legal basis. Upon receipt, Kick would have been legally obliged to comply immediately and to report back to the authority on the action taken.

The use of Article 9 by national authorities would not have been without precedent, though its application remains recent and uneven across Member States. In Germany, state media authorities have already begun issuing Article 9 orders to compel the removal of illegal online content, operating through newly established procedural frameworks dedicated to such orders. In cooperation with the Central Reporting Office for Criminal Content on the Internet (ZMI) of the Federal Criminal Police Office, more than 600 items of content deemed inadmissible under media law have been removed via official platform reporting channels, and over 200 hearing notifications have been sent as part of order procedures under Article 9 of the DSA (Kollmann, 2024). In France, however, the absence of such an order may reflect a selective gap in the DSA's enforcement framework as we will see in the next section.

Furthermore, in France, under Article 6-3 of the 2004 Law for Confidence in the Digital Economy (LCEN), any other public authority (ARCOM included), could have referred the matter to the president of the judicial court, who, ruling under the expedited procedure (*procédure accélérée au fond*), may order any measures necessary to prevent or put an end to harm caused by the content of an online communication service. This mechanism is reinforced by Article 6-4 of the LCEN, amended by the 2024 law aimed at securing and regulating the digital space (SREN), which creates a second layer of intervention once a judicial decision has been issued. It empowers the administrative authority to request not only hosting providers, but also access providers, search engines, and any other actors identified by the court to block access to the targeted service or to dereference the associated URLs. The law even provides for the publication of a list of services subject to such orders and imposes disclosure obligations on advertisers who continue commercial relationships with them. In practice, this framework allows French authorities to act indirectly against online services located abroad by compelling intermediaries operating or offering services on the French territory to implement blocking or dereferencing measures.

In May 2025, the Paris Judicial Court granted media and entertainment group Canal+ a landmark ruling ordering five VPN providers to block 203 domain names linked to illegal sports streaming. The decision recognised VPN providers as technical intermediaries and extended liability measures previously applied to Internet Service Providers (ISP), Domain Name System (DNS) providers, and Content Delivery Networks (CDN) (Bascou, 2025; Canal+, 2025). This demonstrates that, where a platform itself is unreachable, courts can still act indirectly by compelling other intermediaries to enforce judicial orders. This further demonstrates that the ARCOM's assertion that its powers were rendered ineffective by Kick's failure to appoint an EU legal representative was not insurmountable. The period between the opening of the case in

December 2024 and Jean Pormanove's death in August 2025 seemed to have afforded the authorities enough time to mobilise these tools effectively.

d. Political Authorities

Finally, this case also exposes inaction by some of France's highest politicians. During its first investigation in December 2024, Mediapart tried to contact Clara Chappaz, then Minister for AI and Digital Technologies, to alert the government to Kick's activities and the violent content broadcast on Jean Pormanove's channel. They received no response and no concrete action followed.

This silence is particularly troubling given France's long-standing practice of maintaining informal and ad hoc channels of influence with major digital platforms, allowing political authorities to bypass formal procedures and pressure companies into compliance. For example, Telegram founder Pavel Durov recently claimed that French intelligence services had approached him with a request to block lawful anti-government channels ahead of the Moldovan elections, offering in return to "say good things" about him to the judge overseeing his arrest in France in August 2024 (Reuters, 2025). Similarly, Snapchat's Public Affairs Manager, Sarah Bouchahoua, acknowledged maintaining direct links with the French Ministry of the Interior (in charge of security and territorial administration), to remove content during the 2023 riots (Bouchahoua, 2023). This was later confirmed by Jean-Noël Barrot, then Minister for Digital Transition and Telecommunications, who explained before the Senate that the government had asked platforms "to go a little further", anticipating the provisions of the forthcoming DSA. The minister congratulated the platforms for having "responded to these obligations", reporting the removal of thousands of posts and the suspension of hundreds of accounts in the space of a week (Mollier-Sabet, 2023). This explicit reference to the DSA by Jean-Noël Barrot is meaningful as it demonstrates that French political authorities were already invoking it as a legitimising tool for informal cooperation with platforms. The 2023 intervention thus establishes a direct link between French national political action and the DSA's emerging compliance culture, showing that the government actively sought to anticipate and apply its principles before it became applicable across the EU.

State interventions in France have also occurred through formal legal mechanisms. In April 2024, the French government ordered the complete blockade of TikTok in New Caledonia under the 1955 State of Emergency Law, as amended in 2017 to permit the blocking of online platforms that "provoke or glorify acts of terrorism". In practice, critics argued that this provision was used to suppress the digital communications of protestors, demonstrating how emergency powers originally intended for counter-terrorism purposes can be repurposed to curb political dissent.

The Conseil d'État⁸ subsequently ruled that the government's decision had constituted an infringement on users' fundamental rights and freedoms (Benedetti Valentini, 2025).

Beyond these cases lies a dense web of links between France's political sphere and the digital industry. Snapchat's Sarah Bouchahoua served as head of the Paris branch of "Les Jeunes avec Macron" (the youth wing of Emmanuel Macron's movement) before becoming parliamentary assistant from 2018 to 2020. During that period, she contributed to drafting the controversial "Avia Law" aimed at combating online hate speech which several of its provisions were later struck down by the Constitutional Council,⁹ which ruled that they risked infringing "the exercise of freedom of expression and communication in a manner that is neither necessary, appropriate, nor proportionate" (Untersinger and Piquard, 2020). At TikTok, Éric Garandeau, former adviser to President Sarkozy, and former President of the National Centre for Cinema (CNC), now serves as the company's leading cultural policy strategist in France. Laurent Solly, previously Chief of Staff to President Sarkozy, has occupied senior executive roles at Meta in France and Europe for more than 10 years. Aurore Denimal, now Public Policy Manager at Meta France, formerly worked at both the National Assembly and the Ministry of Defence. Benoît Tabaka, Secretary General of Google France, has a long public-sector career behind him, having served at the Constitutional Council, and later as Secretary General of the National Digital Council (CNNum). The list goes on.

The close circulation of elites between government and industry fosters mutual familiarity and access, making direct contact between public officials and platform executives not only possible but routine. In the aftermath of Jean Pormanove's death, this dynamic was clearly on display. Shortly after the incident, Minister Clara Chappaz announced publicly on X that she had "contacted the platform's executives to obtain explanations". Her statement confirms that, when the political will exists, the state can indeed reach out directly to platforms to put things in order. Clara Chappaz later defended the government's limited response, claiming that "as a minister, you cannot decide to shut down a site. There's no red button" (Chappaz, 2025). Yet, as the examples above make clear, there is indeed a button, perhaps not red, but one that the state has pressed when its own authority or image was at stake. This is not to suggest that informal channels of communication between governments and platforms are desirable as indeed they raise concerns about transparency and democratic oversight of digital platforms that function as public spaces. But to dismiss them as non-existent or insignificant would be naïve.

In the case of Jean Pormanove, where the threat was not to the state but to a vulnerable citizen, it was only after the tragedy, once public scrutiny began to mount over the government's

⁸ The supreme administrative jurisdiction in France.

⁹ The highest constitutional authority in France.

inaction, that Clara Chappaz issued a public statement, referred the matter to the ARCOM, and filed a report through PHAROS. This delay in action reveals a political system more willing to deploy its power to preserve its legitimacy than to protect those it is meant to serve.

Viewed through this lens, the DSA exposes its double edge. If the state uses it to intervene forcefully only when its own stability is threatened, the DSA could become not a shield for citizens but an instrument of selective governance reinforcing state authority without ensuring public protection.

And therein lies the danger. Today, these powers may rest in the hands of the Good; tomorrow, they could be wielded by the Bad and the Ugly. The misuse of such discretion, particularly in illiberal or crisis contexts, would set anti-democratic precedents that the DSA was meant to prevent. Or was it?

4. Conclusion

Raphaël “Jean Pormanove” Graven died on camera, in front of thousands, in one the most regulated digital market in the world. His death was not a hidden tragedy buried in the Internet’s dark corners; it was a public spectacle of violence, streamed in real time on a platform that turned shock into entertainment. Shock runs through this story in more than one sense. It was what drew audience: shock as content. It was what generated profit: shock as currency. And it may also have been your reaction while reading this story: shock that such cruelty could be broadcast live, and shock that nothing was done to stop it. The gap between the DSA ambition and its real-life application should give pause to anyone who believes that texts alone guarantee accountability.

This paper has retraced the chain of accountability. Kick, the platform that built its business on decadence, ignored its moral and legal duties, profiting from humiliation, abuse, and ultimately death. The French media regulator, ARCOM, now recognised as the national Digital Services Coordinator, failed to act despite its strengthened mandate. The police and judiciary hesitated. Politicians, meanwhile, proved more interested in invoking the DSA to defend their own interests than in protecting a vulnerable citizen.

Jean Pormanove has exposed, with deadly clarity, the limits of the EU’s digital governance model. The DSA may represent the most sophisticated framework ever conceived for online accountability, its effectiveness depends on the willingness, and capacity, of institutions to act. In the world that failed Jean Pormanove, every actor could plausibly claim that responsibility lay elsewhere. In such a system, where everyone is responsible, no one is. If the EU’s vision of a

“human-centric” digital environment is to mean anything,¹⁰ it must demonstrate that human suffering cannot be commodified with impunity. The EU cannot claim moral leadership in digital governance while tragedies like this one unfold in its own backyard.

None of this means that regulation is the answer to everything. Nor does this paper suggest that more laws, more rules, or heavier censorship will magically prevent such tragedies. But it does mean facing the reality that platforms like Kick are not neutral intermediaries. They are active, commercial infrastructures that curate, amplify, and monetise content. Their algorithms and moderation choices are not technical artefacts but editorial decisions and deliberate choices about what rises and what sinks, about whose voices are amplified and whose are ignored. When those decisions enable the humiliation and degradation of vulnerable individuals for profit, the question is not whether we are regulating too much, but whether we are willing to enforce the standards we already claim to uphold.

What happened to Jean Pormanove should never have been possible. His death is a mirror held up to a system that has confused regulation with justice, and oversight with care. The warning is clear: until neglect becomes more costly than action, the next tragedy is not a question of *if*, but *when*.

Homo homini monstrum.

¹⁰ As stated by the European Commission. See: https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/digital-and-infrastructure/responsible-digitalisation_en.

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